
FACTORS IN THE FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN A FUTURE TEACHER

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7352583>

Yulbarsova Khurshida Abdullajonovna,
Doctor of philosophy (PhD),
Fergana state university

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the communicative competence in future teachers, able, easily, active and independently to think, to modulate, to transform educational process and also independently generate and embody modern ideas and technology in teaching.

Keywords: *competence, communicative competence, modern educational system of communication, communicative activity.*

Professional and qualified preparation of teachers for pedagogical activity carries a number of features that are associated with the quality of his knowledge, abilities in the studied subjects. And the formation of communicative competence is necessary for a more productive work of the teacher in the pedagogical sphere, being especially important for the full development of the comprehensively developed younger generation. It should be noted that modern requirements for the preparation of students - future teachers are changing rapidly, because society needs not just for a professional teacher, but also a competent specialist who has a variety of teaching methods using as innovative technologies.

Analyzing the views of domestic and foreign researchers, we can say that communicative competence is interpreted as a certain amount of integration competencies, supplemented by empathic and reflective abilities, which develops during special educational classes, thereby communicative competence can be considered as follows:

personality characteristics that determine its
outstanding success in communication;

a combination of abilities, personal qualities and
acquired competencies;

a combination of abilities, personal qualities and
acquired competencies;

As we can see, communicative competence is:

- firstly, the totality of human competences in the field of communication, which are necessary to carry out certain activities;
- secondly, it is part of a person’s interpersonal life experience obtained in the process of interaction with other people, his independent activity in various situations;
- thirdly, these are the socio-personal qualities of a person that regulate his entire system of relations with the world, as well as with himself;
- fourthly, this ability as a personality trait that determines its capabilities in a wide variety of activities, with its indispensable compliance with this type of activity;
- fifth, this is a person’s willingness to organize his speech behavior in the presence of real life situations in accordance with the above components. It is worth noting that the presence of the presented components is a prerequisite for the successful implementation of productive and professional activities of a person in a certain area.

In the article, we also determined that “communicative competence” necessarily includes subsections of a number of psychological and pedagogical concepts, and above all, these are the concepts of “*ability*” and “*readiness*”.

The concept of "ability" includes the following characteristics:

- “these are the individual psychological (personality) properties of a person (anatomical, physiological, regulatory, physical, psychophysiological, etc.), which determine the mental capabilities of a person in various types of activities” [3; 434];
- “these properties are to some extent determined by the knowledge, skills and abilities of the individual, but are not reduced to them; they are manifested in the speed and strength of mastering the methods of a certain activity” and these

properties “determine a person’s capabilities, are a condition for his successful performance of one or another productive activity” [2; 321];

The concept of “readiness” means an action with the mobilization of “all psychophysiological and functional systems for the upcoming fulfillment of a certain action, an operational setting, an afferent synthesis of the conditions for the effective fulfillment of an upcoming action, and an increase in sensitivity to the conditions of activity”. [3; 74]

And "readiness for activity itself is a complex dynamic system that includes the intellectual, emotional, motivational and volitional sides of the psyche." [3; 55]

As we can see, these factors are inextricably linked, and act as special integral qualities of competence. But at the same time, “to be able” and “to be ready” for some activity is not the same thing. The concept of “readiness” can “limit the range of individual psychological properties of an individual, leaving knowledge, skills, and abilities beyond its limits. So, a person can be well technically prepared and educated, but little capable of any activity”. [1; 247]

The analysis of these concepts allows us to conclude that a person can be ready to carry out any activity, but for this he will need to mobilize all his personal qualities and mental abilities in order to successfully complete the task of the activity. Thus, based on the above provisions, we determine the structure of communicative competence, which includes the following components (Scheme 1).

Communicative competence cannot be considered the final characteristic of a human person. The acquisition of communicative competence is a progressive movement from point A to point B, from actual events of a personal nature to the results of awareness of the data of occurring events, which are fixed in the cognitive structures of the human psyche in the form of certain competencies that can serve the person in his further contacts with surrounding people, because the ability to learn in communicative situations increases as a person develops cultural, including ideological and moral norms and the law polarity of public life.

It should be noted that the modern requirements for the training of students - future teachers, are changing rapidly, because society needs not just a professional teacher, but also a competent specialist who owns a variety of teaching methods. In connection with this provision, the effective preparation of bachelor teachers for their future teaching activities plays a crucial role. In conclusion, it can be said that,

1. The study reveals the structural components of "communication activity":

- a) the subject of communication is another person;
- b) communicative motives - that's why communication takes place;
- c) self-awareness and self-esteem;
- d) initiative and response actions;
- e) education of the spiritual, moral and material nature of communication;
- f) means of communicative activity - these are operations by means of which communication actions are carried out.

2. Both verbal communication, where human speech is used, and non-verbal communication, in which various non-verbal signs and symbols are used, are distinguished. Speech, as you know, is the most universal means of communication, because during the transmission of information through speech, the least sense of communication is lost.

3. Competence in all types of communication can consist in achieving three basic levels of adequacy of interlocutors for communication:

- a) communicative;
- b) interactive;
- c) perceptual.

4. In modern scientific and methodological literature, we single out the integration characteristics of competencies:

- social competencies related to the ability of a person to take responsibility, to participate in the joint adoption of any decisions;

- competencies that regulate life in society, and designed to prevent the spread of feelings of intolerance, and also contribute to a special understanding of a person's readiness to live with other people who are representatives of other cultures, languages and religions;

- competencies that determine a person's written and oral communication skills, which are especially important in modern public life and professional activity;

- competencies that are associated with the emergence of an innovative information society, where the possession of new technologies is especially priority;

- competencies that realize a person’s ability to learn throughout his life, not only in his chosen profession, but also in his personal and public life.

5. It is also important to note that “communicative competence is a complex entity that includes the following components:

- *subject* (non-verbal competence),
- *linguistic* (speech competence),
- *socio-cultural* (including competences in the field of social relations, communication psychology),
- *pragmatic* (directly related to the communication of the addressee and the addressee of speech in a certain situation - motives, attitudes and goals of communication).

6. In general, communicative competence can consist of the following integration features:

- a) Socio-psychological forecasting of the communicative situation, on the basis of which communication should take place.
- b) Socio-psychological programming of the process of communication itself, where emphasis is placed on the originality of the communicative situation itself.
- c) Implementation of the features of socio-psychological management of communication processes in a communicative situation.

7. Clarification of the essence of the concept of “communicative competence” of a teacher allows us to present its essential structure, which helps to understand the ways of its improvement. The structure of the teacher's communicative competence must necessarily include integration competencies for the following actions:

- interpersonal perception and assessment of the situation of communicative communication (perceptual component);
- introspection and self-esteem of their behavior in the process of communicative communication (reflective component);
- selection of adequate means for interpersonal communication;
- management of the process of communication and the corresponding regulation of human behavior (behavioral component).

REFERENCES

1. Гиппенрейтер Ю.Б. Введение в общую психологию / Ю.Б. Гиппенрейтер. – М.: ЧеРо, 1996. – С. 247.

2. Коджаспирова Г.М., Коджаспиров А.Ю. Педагогический словарь: для студ. высш. и сред. пед. учеб. заведений / Г.М.Коджаспирова, А.Ю. Коджаспиров. – 2-е изд., стер. – М.: Академия, 2005. – С. 321.
3. Психологический энциклопедический словарь / Под ред. М.И.Еникеева – М.: Изд-во Проспект, 2006. – С. 434.
4. Юлбарсова Х. А. (2016). Формирование коммуникативной компетенции будущих учителей в процессе их подготовки к технологии эффективного общения. *Молодой ученый*, (20), 756-757.
5. Yulbarsova K.A. (2020). SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH METHOD AND MEANS IN SOCIAL WORK. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(4), 206-213.
6. Юлбарсова Х. А. (2020). КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТЬ КАК НЕОБХОДИМАЯ СОСТАВЛЯЮЩАЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ. *Интернаука*, 23(152 часть 2), 54.
7. Юлбарсова, Х. А. (2015). Теоретическая сущность и структура коммуникативной компетентности и особенности ее формирования. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (11).
8. Юлбарсова, Х. А. (2021). ВОЛОНТЁРСТВО-ЭТО ФАКТОР ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ У БУДУЩИХ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ. *Человек. Наука. Социум*, (1), 228-237.
9. Юлбарсова, Х. А. (2021). РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ПРОЦЕССА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ У БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ. *East European Scientific Journal*, 4(3 (67)), 36-40.
10. Юлбарсова, Х. А. (2021). ПРИНЦИП ГУМАНИЗМА КАК ФАКТОР ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ ПЕДАГОГОВ. *Наука сегодня: вызовы и решения [Текст]: материалы меж*, 61.
11. Юлбарсова, Х. А. (2017). КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТЬ КАК НЕОБХОДИМАЯ СОСТАВЛЯЮЩАЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ-БАКАЛАВРА. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (12-3), 84-88.
12. Обидова, Г. К. Гуманизация и интеграция в экологизации образовательного процесса. *ХАБАРШЫСЫ*, 55.

-
13. Обидова, Г. К. (2016). Закономерности и принципы становления и развития экологической культуры будущих учителей в системе педагогического образования. *Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук*, (3-5), 82-85.
 14. Обидова, Г. (2021). Развитие экологической культуры в образовательных моделях развитых стран мира. *Общество и инновации*, 2(10/S), 251-256.
 15. Обидова, Г. К., & Гайбуллаева, М. Ф. (2021). Хорижий тилларни ўқитишда экологик таълимнинг педагогик психологик имкониятлари. *Scientific progress*, 2(7), 312-321.
 16. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2021). Analysis of Effective Ways to Develop Students' Environmental Culture in Foreign Language Teaching. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE*, 2(12), 37-43.
 17. Maxkamova, D., & Obidova, G. (2022). EXPRESSION OF “RESPECT” DURING ONLINE LESSONS ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ “УВАЖЕНИЯ” ВО ВРЕМЯ ОНЛАЙН-УРОКОВ ONLAYN DARSLAR DAVOMIDA “HURMAT” IFODASI. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(1), 454-458.